

KTZM QO‘LLANILADIGAN OBYEKTlardagi AVARIYADA KIMYOVIY HOLATNI BAHOLASH.

Muradov Sirojiddin

Qarshi muhandislik-iqtisodiyot institute,

“Mehnat muhofazasi va texnika xavfsizligi” kafedrası stajyor-o‘qituvchisi.

sirojiddinmuradov0@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4270-8600>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701651>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada, kimyoviy holatni baholash, taxlil qilish usllari hamda sano‘at obektlarida REM, (KTZM)ni aniqlash, kimyoviy holatni baholashda havoning turg‘unlik darajasi belgilari haqida muallifning nazariy, ummumlashtiruvchi fikrlari keltirilgan. Maqola mehnat muhoazasi va texnika xavfsizligi yunalishlari talablari, mehnat muhofazasi va xavfsizlik mutaxassislari hamda keng izlanuvchilar uchun muljallangan.

Kalit so‘zlar va iboralar: “Kimyoviy holat, kimyoviy holatni baholash, xavfsizlik, KTZM, izotermiya, konveksiya, sanoat korxonolari, agressiv moddalar”.

ASSESSMENT OF THE CHEMICAL SITUATION IN AN ACCIDENT IN FACILITIES USING KTZM.

Abstract. In this article, the author's theoretical and general opinions are presented about methods of chemical state assessment, analysis, determination of REM, (KTZM) in industrial objects, signs of air stagnation level in chemical state assessment. The article is intended for the requirements of labor protection and technical safety directions, labor protection and safety specialists, and general readers.

Key words and phrases: "Chemical state, assessment of chemical state, safety, KTZM, isotherm, convection, industrial enterprises, aggressive substances."

ОЦЕНКА ХИМИЧЕСКОЙ СИТУАЦИИ ПРИ АВАРИИ НА ОБЪЕКТАХ, ИСПОЛЬЗУЮЩИХ КТЗМ.

Аннотация. В статье изложены теоретические и общие мысли автора об оценке химического состояния, методах анализа, определении РЗМ (КТЗМ) на промышленных объектах, признаках уровня застоя воздуха при оценке химического состояния. Статья предназначена для требований направлений охраны труда и технической безопасности, специалистов по охране труда и технике безопасности, а также широкого круга читателей.

Ключевые слова и фразы: «Химическое состояние, оценка химического состояния, безопасность, КТЗМ, изотерма, конвекция, промышленные предприятия, агрессивные вещества».

Kirish. Kimyoviy holat deb- dushman tomonidan kimyoviy qurollar ishlatilganda, yoki kimyoviy obyektlarda halokat yuz berganda atrof-muhitga kuchli ta’sir etuvchi zaharli moddalar (KTZM) tarqalganligi natijasida hosil bo‘lgan sharoitga aytiladi.

Kimyoviy holatni baholash deganda – kuchli ta’sir etuvchi zaharli moddalarni odamlarga, hayvonlarga, suv va boshqa obyektlarga ta’sir etish darajasini aniqlash hamda kimyoviy hujum

yoki ishlab chiqarish tarmoqlaridagi falokat oqibatlarini tugatish uchun eng maqbul uslubni tanlash tushuniladi.

Tadqiqot metodlari. Tadqiqot jarayonida ilmiy va o'quv-uslubiy adabiyotlar tahlili, pedagogik-tarixiy kuzatuv, umumlashtirish, metodlaridan foydalanildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari va muhokamalar. KTZM ishlatiladigan obyektlardagi avariya kimyoviy holatni baholash, fuqarolarni zaharlanish o'choqlarida bo'lishlari mumkin bo'lgan holda, ularni himoyalanihini tashkil etish maqsadida o'tkaziladi.

Kimyoviy holatni baxolashda bashorat usuli bo'yicha zaxarlangan xavoning tarqalishi uchun qulay bo'lgan sharoitda (inversiya, shamol tezligi 1m/s. da) ob'ektdagi barcha KTZM zaxiralarining tashqariga chiqib ketishi (tukilish) okibatlarini o'rganish orkali aniqlanadi.

KTZM saqlanadigan zaxirasining falokatini baxolash, xaqiqatda sodir bo'lgan vaziyatda utkaziladi. Bunda zaxarli moddalarning aniq miqdori va ob xavo sharoitlari xisobga olinadi.

SHunga xam ahamiyat berish lozimki, qaynash xarorati 20°S dan past bo'lgan zaxarli moddalarni (masalan, fozgen, vodorod ftorid va shunga uxshashlar) to'kilishi bilan juda oz vaqt mobaynida bug'lanib ketadi va bug'langan zaxarli modda miqdori, uning tukilgan suyuq miqdoriga teng bo'ladi. Agar qaynash harorati 20°S dan yuqori bo'lgan (uglerod (IV) sulfid, sinil kislotasi va boshqalar) va qaynamaydigan zaxarli suyuqliklar (ammiak, xlor, oleum va xokazolar) usha ob'ekt hududi bo'ylab tarqaladi va xavoning yer ustki qatlamini zaharlaydi.

KTZM bo'lgan joylardagi kimyoviy xolatni baxolashda, kimyoviy zaxarlangan hudud o'lchamini, kimyoviy shikastlanish uchog'ini, zaxarli havoning hududga yetib kelish va shikastlash vaqtini xamda kimyoviy shikastlanish uchoqlarida fuqarolarni talafotlanish extimollari ko'zda tutiladi.

Shunga ham ahamiyat berish lozimki, qaynash harorati 20° S dan past bo'lgan zaxarli moddalarni (masalan, fozgen, vodorod ftorid va shunga o'xshashlar) to'kilishi bilan juda oz vaqt mobaynida bug'lanib ketadi va bug'langan zaxarli modda miqdori, uning to'kilgan suyuq miqdoriga teng bo'ladi. Agar qaynash harorati 20° S dan yuqori bo'lgan (uglyerod (IV) sul'fid, sinil kislotasi va boshqalar) va qaynamaydigan zaxarli suyuqliklar (ammiak, xlor, oleum va h.k.) o'sha obyekt hududi bo'ylab tarqaladi va havoning yer ustki qatlamini zaharlaydi.

KTZM bo'lgan joylardagi kimyoviy holatni baholashda, kimyoviy zaharlangan hududni o'lchami, kimyoviy shikastlanish o'chog'i, zaxarli havoni hududga etib kelish vaqti, shikastlash vaqti hamda kimyoviy shikastlanish o'choqlarida fuqarolarni talafatlanish ehtimollari ko'zda tutiladi.

Ochiq joyda KTZM bilan zaharlangan havoning tarqalish chuqurligi (KTZM idishi himoyalannagan, Shamol tezligi 1m/s, izotermiya)*

1-jadval

KTZM nomi	Idishdagi KTZM miqdori (obyektda), (Tona)					
	5	10	25	50	75	100
Xlor, fozgen	4,6	7	11,5	16	19	21
Ammiak	0,7	0,9	1,3	1,9	2,4	3
Oltinugurt (II) oksid	0,8	0,9	1,4	2	2,5	3,5
Vodorod sulfid	1,1	1,5	2,5	4	5	8,8

* Izoh: inversiyada havo qatlamining tarqalish chuqurligi taxminan 5 barobar katta, konveksiyada esa izotermiyaga nisbatan 5 marta kichik bo'ladi.

Havoning vertikal turg'unlik darajasini shamol tezligiga bog'liqligi (holatlar uchun to'g'rilovchi koeffitsient).

2-jadval

Havoning vertikal turg'unlik darajasi	Shamol tezligi, m/s					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Inversiya	1	0,6	0,45	0,38	-	-
Izotermiya	1	0,71	0,55	0,5	0,45	0,41
Konveksiya	1	0,7	0,62	0,55	-	-

Ba'zi KTZM larning parchalanish vaqti (Shamol tezligi – 1m/s)*

3-jadval

KTZM nomi	Saqlanish turi	
	Himoyalangan	Himoyalangan
Xlor	1,3	22
Fozgen	1,4	23
Ammiak	1,2	20
Oltinugurt (IV) oksid	1,3	20
Vodorod sulfid	1	19

*Izoh. SHamol tezligi 1 m/s.dan yuqori bo'lganda quyidagi to'g'rilovchi koeffitsientlardan foydalaniladi:

4-jadval

Shamol tezligi m/s	1	2	3	4	5	6
To'g'rilovchi koeffitsient	1	0,7	0,55	0,43	0,37	0,32

Ilova : Shamol tezligi 1m/s dan yuqori bo'lganda quyidagi to'g'rilovchi koeffitsientlar olinadi:

KTZM ta'siridagi shikastlanish chog'ida fuqarolarning talofotlanish soni, foiz *
Odamlarning joylashgan sharoiti fuqarolarning gazniqob bilan ta'minlanganligi, foiz

5-jadval

Odamlarning joylashgan Sharoiti	Fuqarolarning gazniqob bilan ta'minlanganligi, foiz								
	0	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90
Ochiq joyda	90-100	75	65	58	50	40	35	25	18
InShootlarda, oddiy boshpanada	50	40	35	30	27	22	18	14	9

*Izoh: shikastlanish chog'ida odamlarning taxminiy talofotlanish darajasi (foiz): yengil darajada shikastlanish-25; O'rtacha va og'ir darajada-40; O'lim bilan yakunlanadigan holatda-35.

6-jadval

Shamol tezligi	Inversiya		Izotermiya		Konveksiya	
	R<10km	R>10km	R<10km	R>10km	R<10km	R>10km
1m/s	2	2.2	1.5	2	1.5	1.8
2m/s	4	4.7	3	4	3	3.5
3m/s	6	7	4.5	6	4.5	5
4m/s	-	-	6	8	-	-
5m/s	-	-	7.5	10	-	-
6m/s	-	-	9	12	-	-

Ilova : Zaxarli xavoning urtacha tezligi.

Xulosa. Kuchli ta'sir etuvchi zaharli moddalar bilan ishlaydigan sanoat tarmoqlarida nafaqat avariya oqibatidan fuqarolarga qavf-xatar keltirishi mumkin, balki shu tarmoqlardan chiqindi maqsulotlar xam (atmosfera yoki suv qavzalariga chiqarib yuborilishi) atrof muqitni va tabiatni ifloslantirishi oqibatida insonlar qayotiga jiddiy xavf soladi. Bu borada ayniqsa, metallurgiya, kimyo, biotexnologiya, rezina-texnika, neftni qayta ishlovchi va boshqa sanoat tarmoqlarining salbiy ta'siri juda kattadir. Respublikamizdagi ayrim sanoati rivojlangan ayrim shaharlarda, jumladan, Samarqand, Farqona, Andijon, Qo'qon, Angren, Olmaliq, Chirchiq, Navoiy va boshqa shaxarlarda havoning ifloslanish darajasi me'yoridan 1,5-2 marta xatto ayrim joylarda 3-6 marta ortiq.

REFERENCES

1. Xidirova Dildora, Muradov Sirojiddin. O'zbekiston respublikasi hududida seysmoaktiv hududlar va zilzilaning xavfliligi//Innovative Development in Educational Activities. 2024. 167-172
2. Muradov S. ЭCONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PROFITS IN THE FIELD OF LABOR PROTECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – T. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1239-1245.
3. Мурадов, С. (2024). PRINCIPLES OF ENSURING THE SAFETY OF USING LIFTING CRANES IN CONSTRUCTION-ASSEMBLY WORKS. MODERN SCIENCE AND RESEARCH, 3(2), 933–939. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684936>
4. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН учитель-стажер. Каршинский инженерно-экономический институт кафедра «Охрана труда и техника безопасности» Республики Узбекистан. (2024). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ГРУЗОПОДЪЕМНЫХ КРАНОВ В СТРОИТЕЛЬНО-МОНТАЖНЫХ РАБОТАХ. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10684166>
5. Muradov Sirojiddin. Mehanatni muhofaza qilishning tashkiliy-psixologik asoslaridagi mavjud muammolar//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 133-137.
6. Muradov Sirojiddin. Mehnat sharoitlari va muhitini “kaizen” usuli yordamida takomillashtirishning innovatsion yechimlari//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”.2023. 249-253.

7. Muradov Sirojiddin. Mehnatni muhofaza qilish sohasida yuk ortish va tushirish ishlaridagi yukchilar uchun ishlarning xavfsizligi kategori va qoidalari tahlili//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 232-242
8. Muradov Sirojiddin. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o‘rganish//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 243-248
9. Muradov Sirojiddin. Sanoat korxonalarini rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 146-150
10. Muradov Sirojiddin. Xavfli sanoat korxonalarida ishchilarni xavfli gaz va zaxarli moddalar ta‘siridan himoya qilishga qaratilgan inovatsion yechimlar//“Ekologiya, aholi xavfsizligi va mehnat muhofazasining hozirgi kundagi dolzarb masalalari va istiqbollari”. 2023. 402-405
11. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o‘g‘li. Sanoat korxonalarini rahbar va mutaxassislarining mehnat muhofazasi bo‘yicha bilimlarini tekshirishni raqamli texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning ahamiyati// Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. 2023/10/26. 180-183
12. Мурадов Сирожиддин. Определение отдыха и отпусков на основании нового трудового кодекса// Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. 2023/10/26. 17-21
13. MURADOV SIROJIDDIN HUSAN O‘G‘LI. Mehnatni muhofaza qilishning rivojlanish tarixiy bosqichlarini o‘rganish// Aholi bandligi sohasidagi davlat siyosatining amalga oshirishning dolzarb masalalari. 2023/10/26. 8-16
14. Muradov, S. (2023). ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI AVARIYALARNI O‘RGANISH VA TAHLIL QILISH. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(16), 474–477. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/5015>
15. Muradov Sirojiddin. Ishlab chiqarishdagi avariyalarni o‘rganish va tahlil qilish// Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(16), 474–477.
16. Muradov S. ISHLAB CHIQRISHDAGI AVARIYALARNI O‘RGANISH VA TAHLIL QILISH //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 16. – C. 474-477.
17. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 42-47.
18. Sulstonova , D. N., & Siddiqova , M. A. qizi. (2023). COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(14), 109–115. Retrieved from <https://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4394>
19. Sulstonova D. N., qizi Siddiqova M. A. COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL

- CENTERS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 14. – C. 109-115.
20. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o'g'li, Xakimov Xurshid Hamidulla o'g'li, & Siddiqova Madinabonu Asatilla qizi. (2021). NEW INNOVATIVE ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF SIGNALIZATION AND SECURITY SYSTEMS. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability* (2660-9630), 2, 28-30. Retrieved from <http://www.ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/13>
21. Muradov, S. H. o'g'li, & Zayniyev, U. U. o'g'li. (2023). PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(14), 116–119. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4395>
22. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o'g'li, Zayniyev Ulfat Utkir o'g'li. PRINCIPLES OF PASSING AND DOCUMENTING INSTRUCTIONS ON SAFETY TECHNIQUES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*. 2023-11
23. Sirojiddin M., Umurzoq E. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 42-47.
24. Muradov Sirojiddin; Egamberdiyev Umurzoq. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT OF WORKING CONDITIONS AND ENVIRONMENT THROUGH THE KAIZEN METHOD//International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 42-47.
25. Husan o'g'li M. S., Hamidulla o'g'li X. X. Siddiqova Madinabonu Asatilla qizi. NEW INNOVATIVE ENGINEERING SOLUTIONS TO THE PROBLEMS OF SIGNALIZATION AND SECURITY SYSTEMS //European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630). – 2021. – T. 2. – C. 28-30.
26. Husan o'g'li M. S., Shavkat o'g'li E. D. INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – C. 11-17.
27. Muradov, S. H. o'g'li, & Egamov, D. S. o'g'li. (2023). INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT WORKERS FROM DANGEROUS GAS AND TOXIC SUBSTANCES IN HAZARDOUS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES. *Educational Research in Universal Sciences*, 2(14), 340–342. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4443>
28. O'G E. L. A. A. et al. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11.
29. MURADOV SIROJIDDIN HUSAN O'G'LI; ESHPO'LATOV AZIZBEK ADHAM O'G'LI. PHYSIOLOGICAL AND HYGIENE BASIS OF HUMAN LABOR ACTIVITY//International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management.2023.266-273.

30. Rakhimov, O. D., and S. H. Muradov. "Digitalization of Instructions on Labor Protection and Safety Techniques." *European journal of life safety and stability (EJLSS)* 24 (2022): 80-86.
31. O.D. Rakhimov, Muradov S.H. Digitalization of Instructions on Labor Protection and Safety Techniques. // *European journal of life safety and stability (EJLSS)*. 2022. №24. P.80-86.
32. O'G'LI M. S. H. ANALYSIS OF "MEASURES TO ENSURE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF CARGO TRANSPORTATION AND LOADING." // *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9.
33. MURADOV SIROJIDDIN HUSAN O'G'LI. ANALYSIS OF "MEASURES TO ENSURE OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY IN THE FIELD OF CARGO TRANSPORTATION AND LOADING."// *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, TECHNOLOGY AND MANAGEMENT*. Vol. 2 No. 9 (2023). 127-133
34. ЎҒЛИ Р. Х. Ф., СИРОЖИДДИН М. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН // *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10.
35. ЎҒЛИ, РАЖАБОВ ХУРШИД ФАХРИДДИН, and МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН. "ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 2.10 (2023).
36. ЎҒЛИ, Р. Х. Ф., & СИРОЖИДДИН, М. (2023). ИЗУЧЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЯ ТРУДА В КОМПАНИИ ЕВРОПЫ. МУРАДОВ СИРОЖИДДИН. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(10).
37. Rayimkulov A., Murodov S. Some Issues of Safety in the Use of Tower Cranes Used in Construction Projects // *JournalNX*. – С. 301-308.
38. Rayimkulov A., Murodov S. Some Issues of Safety in the Use of Tower Cranes Used in Construction Projects // *JournalNX*. – С. 301-308.
39. Мурадов, Сирожиддин. "ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ." *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management* 2.5 (2023).
40. Мурадов С. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ // *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5.
41. Мурадов, С. (2023). ПРОБЛЕМЫ ТУШЕНИЯ ПОЖАРОВ КЛАССА Е ЛИЧНЫМ СОСТАВОМ ПОЖАРНОЙ ОХРАНЫ В МИРЕ. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(5).
42. Raximov O.D, Muradov S.H. SANOAT KORXONALARI RAHBARI VA MUTAXASSISLARINI MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI BO'YICHA O'QITISH VA BILIMLARINI SINOVDAN O'TKAZISHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH. MONOGRAFIYA.2023.1-96
43. Raximov O.D, Muradov S.H. SANOAT KORXONALARI RAHBARI VA MUTAXASSISLARINI MEHNAT MUHOFAZASI BO'YICHA O'QITISH VA

- BILIMLARINI SINOVDAN O‘TKAZISHNI RAQAMLASHTIRISH// INTELLEKT. MONOGRAFIYA.2023
44. Dustkabilovich, R. O. ., & o`g`li, M. S. H. . (2021). Innovative Technologies in Teachingdirectors and Specialists of Industrial Enterprises on "Labor Protection". European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 80-85. Retrieved from <http://ejlss.indexedresearch.org/index.php/ejlss/article/view/3>
 45. Rakhimov Oktyabr Dustkabilovich; Muradov Sirojiddin Husan o`g`li. Innovative Technologies in Teachingdirectors and Specialists of Industrial Enterprises on "Labor Protection"// European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 2021/12/29. 80-85.
 46. Muradov S.H; Safarov Sh. O‘. MEHNAT SHAROITLARI VA MUHITINI “KAIZEN” USULI YORDAMIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING INNOVATSION YECHIMLARI// PAXTA TOZALASH, TO‘QIMACHILIK VA YENGIL SANOAT SOHALARINING TEXNOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. 2023. 90-92
 47. СИРОЖИДДИН МУРАДОВ. ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ОХРАНА ТРУДЫ НА ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕ КОРЕИ// ХӨДӨЛМӨР, НИЙГМИЙН ХАРИЛЦАА СУДЛАЛ. 2023. 242-247
 48. Muradov Sirojiddin Husan ugli; Odilov Muzaffar. MAIN INDICATORS OF LABOR PROTECTION MEASURES EFFICIENCY// INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCHERS0 2023. 201-206
 49. Sultonova D. N., qizi Siddiqova M. A. COLOR SCHEME IN THE FORMATION OF THE ARTISTIC ENVIRONMENT OF THE INTERIOR OF MODERN EDUCATIONAL CENTERS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 109-115.
 50. Maxmayusufovich E. L. PRIMARY CONCEPTS ABOUT EARTHQUAKES AND THEM ENSURING THE SAFETY OF THE PUBLIC WHEN IT HAPPENS //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10.
 51. Эшмухамедов Л. М. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В ОБЛАСТИ ПРЕДУПРЕЖДЕНИЯ И ЛИКВИДАЦИИ ЧРЕЗВЫЧАЙНЫХ СИТУАЦИЙ //Вестник науки и образования. – 2022. – №. 6-2 (126). – С. 24-27.
 52. Эшмухамедов Л. М. ОХРАНА ТРУДА НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИИ //МОЛОДЕЖЬ. НАУКА. БУДУЩЕЕ. – 2022. – С. 160-164.
 53. Eshmuhamedov L. M. 21-ASR PEDAGOGIKASI: O ‘QITISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 14. – С. 372-376.
 54. Maxmayusufovich E. L. ORGANIZE LABOR PROTECTION IN ENTERPRISES //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11.
 55. Eshmukhamedov L. M. IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION IN THE FIELD OF PREVENTION AND LIMITATION OF EMERGENCY SITUATIONS //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9.

56. Эшмухамидов Л. М. ТЕХНОСФЕРНАЯ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬ ЧЕЛОВЕКА В СОВРЕМЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6.
57. Eshmuxamedov L. M. et al. LABOR PROTECTION IMPROVE WORKING CONDITIONS, INCREASE EMPLOYEES'PRODUCTIVITY, IMPLEMENTATION OF REST REGIME //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 3. – С. 1161-1166.
58. Otabek M. et al. Dynamics And Stability Of A Composite Feed Cylinder In The Feeding Area Of Rotor Spinning Machines //Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results. – 2023. – С. 1152-1157.
59. Рахимов О. Д., Эшмухамедов Л. М., Ашурова Л. МУСТАҚИЛ ТАЪЛИМНИ РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР АСОСИДА ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ: Рахимов Октябр Дусткабилович, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси профессори Эшмухамедов Латиф Маҳмаюсуфович, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси ассистенти Ашурова Лайло, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси ассистенти //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 6.
60. Рахимов О. Д., Эшмухамедов Л. М. ЧЕТ ЭЛ ОЛИЙ ЎҚУВ ЮРТЛАРИДА ТАЪЛИМ СИФАТИНИ БАҲОЛАШ //INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 68-76.
61. Эшмухамедов Л. М. ВЕСТНИК НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ //ВЕСТНИК НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ Учредители: Олимп. – С. 24-27.
62. Джураев Б. Х. ЭВАКУАЦИИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ НА ОБЪЕКТАХ МАССОВОГО ПРЕБЫВАНИЯ ЛЮДЕЙ ПРИ ЧРЕЗВЫЧАЙНЫХ СИТУАЦИЯХ //Проблемы науки. – 2023. – С. 27.
63. Khudaynazarovich J. B. CORRECT CONDUCT OF THE POPULATION IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9.
64. Жураев Б. Х. МЕТОДЫ И СРЕДСТВА ПОДГОТОВКИ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННЫХ ОБЪЕКТОВ К ЧРЕЗВЫЧАЙНЫМ СИТУАЦИЯМ //Вестник науки и образования. – 2022. – №. 6-2 (126). – С. 20-24.
65. Khudaynazarovich J. B. CORRECT CONDUCT OF THE POPULATION IN EMERGENCY SITUATIONS //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9.
66. Khudainazarovich D. J. B. WORK AS THE MAIN CATEGORY OF ERGONOMICS //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5.
67. Khudaynazarovich J. B. RESEARCH OF OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY PROBLEMS OF WORKERS IN AGRICULTURAL INDUSTRIES RESEARCH OF PROBLEMS OF

- LABOR PROTECTION OF WORKERS IN AGRICULTURAL INDUSTRIES //Multidisciplinary and Multidimensional Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 60-71.
68. Норбаев Эшкuvat Курбанович, Хужакулов, Абдулазиз Хаким Угли, “Доля затрат на эксплуатацию техники для подготовки кормов” Life Sciences and Agriculture Страницы. 2020.- 21-24
69. Parakhat Berdimuratov, Bakhtiyar Shaymardanov, Dilshod Ruziyev, Abdulaziz Khujakulov, Irina Gorlova and Ohunjon Usarov “Seeder of exact seeding of seeds of cotton on the crest with drip irrigation” E3S Web of Conferences 264, 04044 (2021)
70. Oktabr Dustkabilovich Raximov, Abdulaziz Hakim Ugli Xujakulov, Вахром Хусанович Shomurotov, Dilrabo Oktabrova Raximova. Неиспользуемые возможности: дистанционного образования в Узбекистане. Научный журнал. 2021.- Страницы 72-75.
71. Abdulaziz Hakim O‘G‘Li Xujaqulov. Muhandislik ta‘lim yo‘nalishi talabalarini kasbiy tanlovga ta‘sir etuvchi omillar. Science and Education. 2023.- Страницы 493-496
72. А.Х.Хужакулов.Значение инновационных технологий в организации самостоятельной работы студентов в системе высшего образования. Вестник науки. 2023.- Страницы 113-117
73. Xujaqulov Abdulaziz Hakim o‘g‘li. Muhandislik yo‘nalishi talabalarining umumkasbiy tayyorgarligiga qo‘yilgan talablar. Prospects and main trends in modern science 2023.- Страницы 60-63
74. Xujaqulov Abdulaziz Hakim o‘g‘li. Umumkasbiy fanlarni o‘qitish orqali talabalar tomonidan shakllanadigan tadqiqotchilik qobiliyatlari. 2023.- Страницы 321-326
75. Ж.У.Шоназаров, А.Х.Хужакулов.Творческая и инновационная деятельность будущего преподавателя и способы достижения профессиональных навыков. 2020.- Страницы 55-60
76. Rakhimov Oktyabr Dustkabilovich, Manzarov Yusufjon Khurramovich, Keldiyarova Malika, Hudjakulov Abdulaziz Hakim Ugli. Modern lectures and methods of organizing problematic lectures. Проблемы науки 2020.- Страницы 46-49.
77. Husanovich S. B., Ravshanovich B. Z., Laylo A. ANALYSIS OF DEVELOPMENTAL EDUCATION MODELS //Проблемы науки. – 2020. – №. 11 (59). – С. 86-90.
78. Rakhimov O. et al. Methodology for using foresight technology in training future ecologists in Uzbekistan //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 462. – С. 03048.
79. Laylo A. ISHLAB CHQARISH XONALARI HAVOSINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH UCHUN KONDITSIONER USKUNASINING ISHINI QIYOSIY TAHLIL QILISH VA UNI MODELLASHTIRISH //Sanoatda raqamli texnologiyalar/Цифровые технологии в промышленности. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 184-192.
80. Rakhimov O. D., Ashurova L. THE MAIN FACTORS AND CRITERIA OF QUALITY EDUCATION //GOLDEN BRAIN. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 31. – С. 163-169.
81. Rakhimov O. et al. Methodology for using foresight technology in training future ecologists in Uzbekistan //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 462. – С. 03048.

82. Ashurova L. ON THE TECHNOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENTIFIC AND CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN STUDENTS //Innovative Development in Educational Activities. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 23. – С. 294-298.
83. Ashurova L. METHODOLOGY OF USING TELECOMMUNICATION STUDY PROJECTS IN INDEPENDENT EDUCATION //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 17. – С. 135-140.
84. Рахимов О. Д., Эшмухамедов Л. М., Ашурова Л. МУСТАҚИЛ ТАЪЛИМНИ РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР АСОСИДА ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ: Рахимов Октябр Дусткабилович, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси профессори Эшмухамедов Латиф Маҳмаюсуфович, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси ассистенти Ашурова Лайло, Қарши муҳандислик-иқтисодиёт институти “Экология ва меҳнат муҳофазаси” кафедраси ассистенти //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 6.
85. Rakhimov O. et al. Methodology for using foresight technology in training future ecologists in Uzbekistan //E3S Web of Conferences. – EDP Sciences, 2023. – Т. 462. – С. 03048.
86. Rakhimov O. D., Kh M. Y., Ashurova L. Initial foresight studies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Modern education (Uzbekistan). – 2021. – №. 4. – С. 101.
87. Dustkobilovich R. O., Laylo A. Types of modern lectures in higher education, technology of their design and organization //Проблемы современной науки и образования. – 2020. – №. 12-1 (157). – С. 41-46.